

Genotoxicity in Pesticide Workers

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Abstract

Pesticides are chemicals used to control agricultural pests. Though use of pesticides improves the magnitude of agricultural products, yet it severely affects the quality of the crop. In order to assess the genetic risk, arising out of the integrated exposure of composite pesticide, the geno-toxicological biomonitoring in human populations can serve as a useful device. Cytogenetic disfigurement in the flowing lymphocytes of the exposed individuals has been widely employed as a biomarker. It's a quick and reliable test that detects the damage caused to DNA by different dosages of pesticide in question.

A positive correlation has been observed between pesticide exposure and chromosomal aberrations (CA), micro-nuclei (MN) and sister chromatid exchanges (SCE) in the cultured lymphocytes isolated from peripheral blood of the exposed individuals.

Keywords: Pesticide, Genotoxicity, Chromosomal Aberrations, Sister Chromatid Exchange.

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